

Automating Finite Element Model Generation with Python

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Abstract. This conference presentation outlines how Python programming was used to automate the creation of a finite element model for modelling masonry wall constructions in a generalised format that can be applied to different wall bonding patterns, while remaining within the instance limits for crack definitions to function. An arbitrary index system was created for the masonry wall, upon which masonry unit features, mortar features, and bonding features were subsequently constructed. It was found that Python scripting was most effective at allowing the reuse of the initially developed detailed micro-model built for the Eindhoven walls to be rapidly adapted to other masonry wall tests and constructions. New models of masonry walls could be constructed in one hour, instead of weeks when done manually.

Background

Front-end programming details are deemed as unimportant from a scientific point of view, and have been traditionally omitted in the presentation of research results. However, at the scales seen in medium-sized masonry walls, defining each brick and mortar segment manually becomes infeasible from a practical standpoint, and is prone to human error. Such automation tasks are critical to effectively and accurately define masonry walls of high complexity in the detailed micro-model. In most finite element software packages, everything is built upon the geometry, where the geometry cannot be changed after initial creation. Furthermore, it is often not possible to import full material properties without recreating them. Scripting model generation solves all of these problems.

The Python programming language was first introduced in 2002 as a high-level programming language, capable of handling various forms of structured data. It has since been implemented inside software tools and provides a standardised for controlling and batch processing within other commercial software. Here, the process of building a masonry wall [1, 2] using Python programming within Abaqus [3, 4] was considered, however, the methodology may be ported to other finite element packages that have also implemented Python programming.

Defining the geometry

For the purposes of programming the model, an index system was created identifying each brick, which does not necessarily follow the default graphical convention, such that it was easy to that associated the brick with the relevant adjacent masonry mortar segments. By using this method, it was possible in accordance with best practices in Finite Element modelling to always define the master surface of the interface to the brick side, while defining the slave surface of the interface to the mortar side. Referencing all objects to an index instead of to a part allowed for increased modelling flexibility, by allowing a lower number of parts,

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while allowing each interaction or interface to be defined uniquely by its relationship to the index.

The index system had to be generic enough that it could accommodate different end stack patterns, either half bricks or full bricks at the wall end, while simultaneously being specific enough to associate bricks correctly with one another. Satisfying these geometry conditions required a different part and index definition whether a simplified micro-model or detailed micro-model was being used. In the case of a detailed micro-model, the conventions Brick Index, Head Joint Index, Bed Joint Index and Junction Index were used.

Fig. 1. Index system developed for defining brick masonry units: (a) Simplified Micro-Model, (b) Detailed Micro-Model.

On the basis of the index system, four parts were created. Modelling required two conditions to be satisfied simultaneously: that the model contain no more than 100 parts total, while no interface may join two surfaces of the same part. In the case of a Simplified Micro-model, brick indices had to be assigned to alternating parts by row and by column as shown in Fig. 1.a. In the case of a Detailed Micro-model, all bricks could be on one part due to the fact that no two bricks ever directly adjoined each other, while the head joints, bed joints and mortar junctions comprised the other three parts, as shown in Fig. 1.b.

Scripting to process results

Results processing with Python scripting is also possible; results were extracted for a loaded surface across all nodes, defined as the same surface used for model loading. In the scenario of an imposed displacement, the reaction force was selected, upon which in post-processing, a summation of the reaction forces at all nodes was taken.

In a static pushover analysis, the step time is linearly proportional to the imposed load or imposed displacement. In this type of analysis, the load or displacement may be achieved by exporting only one set of values, which is by default referenced to the time step.

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